

A STUDY ON CONSUMER AWARENESS AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The term Organic food production not only means avoidance of chemical inputs in the production process, but it refers to all strategies used to maintain biological diversity and replenish the fertility of the soil. "Organic food production is a self-regulated industry with government oversight in some countries, distinct from private gardening. The main objective of the study is to know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food products in Coimbatore district. For this purpose data was collected from a sample of 110 respondents and different statistical used were used to analyse the data. The conclusion is that more consumer awareness programs, reduction in the price for these organic products, effective distribution to all the areas and a better government support in procurement and sale of the organic products will help the organic food manufacturers to have a better market share.

Key Words: Organic Food, Consumer Awareness & Acceptance

Introduction:

Introduction to Organic Products:

Organic food products are products that are produced in a method of farming which avoids the use of chemical fertilizers, and harmful pesticides. It also avoids adding growth regulators and livestock feed additives that stimulate the growth. Irradiation and the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) or products produced from or by GMOs are generally prohibited by organic legislation. Organic agriculture is a systems approach to production that is working towards environmentally, socially and economically sustainable production. Instead, the agricultural systems rely on crop rotation, animal and plant manures, some hand weeding and biological pest control'.

Introduction to Customer Attitude:

Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer's (1) beliefs about, (2) feelings about, (3) and behavioral intentions toward some object--within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object.

Scope of the Study:

The study is about analyzing the perception and awareness of customers towards organic food usage on Coimbatore. This may help the manufacturers of organic foods to develop better production and marketing strategies which will lead to increase in profit of their firm.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the level of acceptance of various factors related to organic food.

- ✓ To analyse the demographic profile of the respondents.
- ✓ To know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Due to time constraint, the sample size is limited to 110 & the study area is restricted to Coimbatore.
- ✓ Respondent may fail to express their opinions and beliefs.
- ✓ There may be a bias in collecting the data.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: The area of the study is Coimbatore city only.

Population of the Study: The population of the study is indefinite.

Sampling Design: For the purpose of this study the data were collected from 110 respondents using random sampling technique.

Sampling Size: The sample size of the research is 110 respondents.

Method of Data Collection:

- ✓ Primary Data: Questionnaire
- ✓ Secondary Data: Books, journals and magazines.

Tools Used for study: Percentage analysis and regression

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 20 years	77	70
	21-30 years	33	30
	Total	110	100
Gender	Male	68	61.8
	Female	42	38.2
	Total	110	100
Marital Status	Married	3	2.7
	Unmarried	107	97.3
	Total	110	100
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	7	6.4
	Up to school	35	31.8
	Graduate	58	52.7
	Others	10	9.1
	Total	110	100
Occupation	Employee	7	6.4
	Business	59	53.6
	Profession	31	28.2
	Others	13	11.8
	Total	110	100
Monthly Income	Less than 10000	15	13.6
	10001-20000	25	22.7
	20001-30000	55	50
	More than 30001	15	13.6
	Total	110	100
Type of family	Joint family	64	58.2
	Nuclear family	46	41.8
	Total	110	100
Members of the family	Less than 3 members	29	26.4
	3-4 members	47	42.7
	5-6 members	26	23.6
	More than 6 members	8	7.3
	Total	110	100
Area of residence	Rural	21	19.1
	Urban	12	10.9
	Semi urban	77	70
	Total	110	100
Awareness towards organic products	Through advertisement	20	18.18
	Through friends and relatives	75	68.18
	Others	15	13.63

	Total	110	100
Level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products	Agree	48	43.6
	Neutral	27	24.5
	Disagree	19	17.3
	Strongly disagree	16	14.5
	Total	110	100
Level of acceptance towards better quality	Strongly agree	11	10
	Agree	45	40.9
	Neutral	33	30
	Disagree	12	10.9
	Strongly disagree	9	8.2
Level of acceptance towards taste of organic products	Total	110	100
	Strongly agree	12	10.9
	Agree	28	25.5
	Neutral	34	30.9
	Disagree	18	16.4
Level of acceptance towards easy availability	Strongly disagree	18	16.4
	Total	110	100
	Strongly agree	11	10
	Agree	35	31.8
	Neutral	29	26.4
Level of acceptance towards nutrition value	Disagree	28	25.5
	Strongly disagree	7	6.4
	Total	110	100
	Strongly agree	7	6.4
	Agree	46	41.8
Level of acceptance towards very expensive of organic products	Neutral	34	30.9
	Disagree	23	20.9
	Total	110	100
	Strongly agree	44	40
	Agree	27	24.5
Frequency of purchasing food products	Neutral	16	14.5
	Disagree	20	18.2
	Strongly disagree	3	2.7
	Total	110	100
	Very often	8	7.3
Interest towards organic foods	Once in a week	31	28.2
	Once in a month	49	44.5
	Rarely	22	20
	Total	110	100
	One year	10	9.1
Facing problem while using organic food product	Two years	54	49.1
	Three years	28	25.5
	More than 3 years	18	16.4
	Total	110	100
	Yes	37	33.67
Satisfaction towards organic foods	No	73	66.36
	Total	110	100
	Yes	97	88.2
	No	13	11.8
	Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about the age of the respondents were out of 110 respondents 70% are from the age group of below 20 years and 30% are from the age group of 21 to 30 years. 61.8% are male and 38.25 are female. 2.7% are married and 97.3% are unmarried. 26.4% are illiterates, 31.8% have completed their schoolings, 52.7% are graduates and 9.1% are from other courses. 6.4% are employees, 53.6% are business people, 28.2% are professionals and 11.8% are doing other jobs. 13.6% are earning less than 10000, 22.7% are earning from 10001-20000, 50% are earning form 20001-30000, 13.6% are earning more than 30001. 58.2% are

from joint family and 41.8% are from nuclear family. 42.7% are having 3-4 members, 23.6% are having from 5-6 members and 7.3% are having more than 6 members in their family. 19.1% are from rural area, 10.9% are from urban area and 70% are from semi urban area. 43.6% agree, 24.5% are neutral, 17.3% disagree and 14.5% strongly disagree. It shows that most 43.6% of the respondents agree for reliability of organic products. 10% strongly agree, 40.9% agree, 30% are neutral, 10.9% disagree and 8.2% strongly disagree. It shows that most 40.9% of the respondents agree for better quality of organic products. 10.9% strongly agree, 25.5% agree, 30.9% are neutral, 16.4% disagree and 16.4% strongly disagree. It shows that most 30.9% of the respondents are neutral towards taste of organic products. 10% strongly agree, 31.8% agree, 26.4% are neutral, 25.5% disagree and 6.4% strongly disagree. It shows that most 31.8% of the respondents agree for easy availability. 6.4% strongly agree, 41.8% agree, 30.9% are neutral, and 20.9% disagree. It shows that most 41.8% of the respondents agree for nutrition value. 14.5% strongly agree, 24.5% agree, 40% are neutral, 18.2% disagree and 2.7% strongly disagree. It shows that most 40% of the respondents are neutral about very expensive of organic products. 7.3% purchase very often, 44.5% purchase once in a week, 28.2% purchase once in a month, and 20% purchase rarely. It shows that most 44.5% of the respondents purchase once in a week. 8.2% purchase through departmental store, 33.6% purchase in super market and 23.6% purchase through other sources. It shows that most 34.5% of the respondents purchase organic products through online. 16.4% said as friends and relatives, 34.5% said as news paper, 36.4% said as television and 12.7% said as other sources. .1% said as one year, 49.1% said as two years, 25.5% said as three years and 16.4% said as more than three years. 22.7% are purchasing organic products if they are less expensive and 77.3% are not purchasing. 33.67% said they are facing problem while using organic food product and 66.36% said that they are not facing problem. 88.2% are satisfied and 11.8% are not satisfied. It shows that most 88.2% of the respondents are satisfied towards organic foods.

Regression:

Comparison between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Acceptance towards Reliability of Organic Products:

H₀: There is no relationship between demographic profile of the respondents and level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.635 ^a	.404	.363	.875	.404	9.869	7	102	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Type of family , Educational qualification , Gender , Monthly income , Marital status , Age , Occupation

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.519	1.241		1.225	.224
	Age	.421	.209	.177	2.017	.046
	Gender	-.962	.221	-.428	-4.350	.000
	Marital status	1.508	.544	.225	2.771	.007
	Educational qualification	-.243	.119	-.164	-2.047	.043
	Occupation	-.825	.158	-.591	-5.221	.000
	Monthly income	.668	.116	.539	5.741	.000
	Type of family	.157	.193	.071	.816	.416

a. Dependent Variable: Level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between demographic profile of the respondents and level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products. There is a relationship between level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products and age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation and monthly income.

Findings:

- ✓ Most 70% of the respondents are from the age group of below 20 years.
- ✓ Most 70% of the respondents are male in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum 52.7% of the respondents are graduates in our survey.
- ✓ Most 53.6% of the respondents are doing business.
- ✓ Maximum 50% of the respondents are earning from 20001-30000 as their monthly income.

- ✓ Most 58.2% of the respondents are from joint family.
- ✓ Maximum 42.7% of the respondents are having 3-4 members in their family.
- ✓ Most 42.7% of the respondents are from semi urban area.
- ✓ Maximum 43.6% of the respondents agree for reliability of organic products.
- ✓ Most 30.9% of the respondents are neutral towards taste of organic products.
- ✓ Maximum 41.8% of the respondents agree for nutrition value.
- ✓ Most 44.5% of the respondents purchase once in a month.
- ✓ Maximum 34.5% of the respondents purchase organic products through online.
- ✓ Most 50% of the respondents purchase fruits.
- ✓ Maximum 36.4% of the respondents said as television for person influencing to buy organic products.
- ✓ Most 49.1% of the respondents said as two years for interest towards organic foods.
- ✓ Maximum 77.3% of the respondents said that they are not purchasing the product even though they are less expensive.
- ✓ Most 36.4% of the respondents agree towards providing healthier food for them and their family by purchasing organic products
- ✓ Maximum 41.8% of the respondents agree for level of acceptance towards organic food taste better than non organic food.
- ✓ Most 37.3% of the respondents are neutral for purchasing organic products means they support local farmers and agriculture.
- ✓ Most 32.7% of the respondents disagree for organic foods caring about environment.
- ✓ Most 35.5% of the respondents agree for fertilize free of organic means
- ✓ Most 44.5% of the respondents are neutral for acceptance towards lower price for organic food.
- ✓ Most 38.2% of the respondents agree for wider product selection for organic food.
- ✓ Most 30.9% of the respondents strongly agree towards strong influence from friends.
- ✓ Most 38.2% of the respondents are neutral for healthiness of organic foods based on scientific evidence.
- ✓ Maximum 66.36% of the respondents said that they are not facing any problem while using organic food product.
- ✓ Most 43.2% of the respondents said that they are facing allergy problems.
- ✓ Maximum 88.2% of the respondents are satisfied towards organic foods.

Suggestions:

Even though of the consumers are aware of organic food products and, its benefits, the study indicates that the consumers feel that the prices of the organic product are on a higher side and fewer advertisements are given about the organic products. Therefore the prices of organic products have to be reduced, so that it is affordable to a common man to purchase.

Moreover more advertisement and brand awareness programs have to be introduced in the market so that, consumers become more aware of the variety of organic product available in the market.

An effective marketing support by the government and a stronger supply chain management will help in the increased availability and sale of the organic products in the market. Moreover a better regulatory framework will enhance the growth of the market for organic products.

Conclusion:

In India there is still a tremendous untapped market for selling these organic products. More consumer awareness programs, reduction in the price for these organic products, effective distribution to all the areas and a better government support in procurement and sale of the organic products will help the organic food manufacturers to have a better market share. When these points are taken into consideration, the industry will see growth in the sales volume and also increased customer base.

Scope for Further Research:

This study on the organic products has provided some important insights into the area of the market about organic food production. Still there is a lot of scope for further research in related areas like the problems faced by the farmers in the production of organic products. Also research can be undertaken in the logistics and supply chain management of marketing these organic products. Also the reach of the organic products in rural areas can be analyzed.

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